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2 **Unveiling viral-host interactions within the ‘microbial dark matter’**

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13 **Abstract**

14 **Viruses control microbial communities in nature^{1,2}. Identification of virus-host pairs**
15 **relies either on their cultivation or on metagenomics and tentative assignment of**
16 **viruses to hosts based on genomic signatures³⁻⁸. Both approaches have severe**
17 **drawbacks to target the uncultured majority. Here, we present an unambiguous way**
18 **to assign viruses to hosts that does not rely on any previous information of either of**
19 **them nor requires their cultivation. First, genomic contents of individual cells present**
20 **in an environmental sample are retrieved by means of single cell genomic**
21 **technologies⁹⁻¹³. Then, individual cell genomes are hybridized against a set of**
22 **individual viral genomes from the same sample, previously immobilized on a**
23 **microarray. Infected cells will yield positive hybridization since they carry viral**
24 **genomes, which can be then sequenced and characterized. Using this method, we have**
25 **pinpointed viruses infecting members of the phylum *Nanohaloarchaeota*, included in**

1 **the recently proposed superphylum DPANN¹² of the so-called ‘microbial dark**
2 **matter’.**

3 Microbes and their viruses constitute the most abundant and diverse group within the
4 biosphere. The interactions among viruses and their microbial hosts have a central
5 influence on biogeochemical cycles, in the control of numbers, diversity and evolution of
6 microbes and even in human health^{1,2}. However, and due to limitations in the available
7 techniques, there is a lack of knowledge on the interaction patterns between viruses and
8 hosts in natural communities since their description relies on the identification of viruses,
9 hosts and viral host ranges³. Although this can be readily accomplished for isolated virus-
10 host pairs, it is not technically feasible for uncultured hosts, which constitute the majority
11 of microbes in the planet. Metagenomic analyses of cellular and viral fractions have
12 provided valuable information on ecologically relevant virus-host interactions, such as in
13 *Prochlorococcus*, from which previous genomic information was available⁴. However,
14 metagenomics do not allow for the unambiguous identification of individual virus-host
15 pairs given the limitations to reconstruct individual viral genomes from short read datasets.
16 Cloning of individual viral genomes from environmental samples into fosmids circumvents
17 some of these limitations⁵⁻⁷ and allows the tentative assignment of viruses to their hosts
18 based on GC content and genomic signature comparisons^{5,7,8} of viral and host genomes.
19 Thus, although very useful, this approach can only be used for assigning viruses to host
20 from which genomic information is previously available. Furthermore, in the absence of
21 further proof, the assignment remains partly speculative given that there are well known
22 virus-host pairs with deviant genomic signatures⁵.

1 To the best of our knowledge, there are only two previous examples in which viruses have
2 been unambiguously assigned to their uncultured host, both using single-cell technologies.
3 In the first case¹⁴, the sequencing of an individual marine protist revealed the presence of a
4 ssDNA virus infecting the host cell at the time of sampling. This finding illustrates the
5 feasibility of describing virus-host systems by isolation of all individuals present in a
6 sample followed by the sequencing of their genomes. However, this approach would
7 require a considerable sequencing and downstream bioinformatics effort since without any
8 previous information, both infected and uninfected hosts would have to be sequenced and
9 analysed. In the second example¹⁵, viruses infecting individual cells residing in the termite
10 hindgut were detected by PCR with specific primers for a viral marker gene. However,
11 there are no viral markers present in all viral genomes and thus, either previous information
12 regarding the viruses present in the analysed sample must be available, or the search has to
13 be restricted to a group of virus with known markers.

14 To circumvent these limitations, we have developed a method that unambiguously assigns
15 viruses to uncultured hosts and does not rely on previous information of any of them nor
16 requires their cultivation. This new approach takes advantage of two high throughput
17 techniques that have proven very useful in microbial ecology: single cell genomics and
18 microarrays. Shortly (Fig. 1), individual cells present in an environmental sample are
19 separated by means of fluorescence activated cell sorting, lysed and their genomes
20 amplified by multiple displacement amplification⁹⁻¹³. In parallel, the viral fraction of the
21 sample is concentrated and individual viral genomes are purified and cloned in fosmids,
22 which are immobilized on a microarray ('virochip'). Then, single amplified genomes
23 (SAGs) from individual cells are hybridized with the 'virochip'. If a single cell is infected

1 by a virus at the time of sampling, then its SAG would yield hybridization signal with the
2 ‘virochip’ (provided that the corresponding virus has been cloned). Further sequencing
3 analysis of the SAG and the corresponding cloned viral genome would allow the
4 identification of both of them and confirm the presence in the sample of such virus-host
5 pair. This approach can be used to look for viruses infecting specific groups of prokaryotes
6 or even to target eukaryotic cells. For this purposes, targeted SAGs could be identified prior
7 to hybridization by means of, for instance, SSU rRNA gene sequencing.

8 We have used this newly developed method to investigate virus-microbe infection network
9 (VMIN) in hypersaline environments. Hypersaline systems harbour the highest densities of
10 viruses reported so far for aquatic samples¹⁶ as well as a diverse assemblage of *Bacteria*
11 and *Archaea*, that is often dominated by the square archaeon *Haloquadratum walsbyi* and
12 contains significant numbers of the recently described *Nanohaloarchaeota*¹⁷. The
13 *Nanohaloarchaea*, along with three other major uncultured prokaryote groups within the
14 unexplored ‘microbial dark matter’, form a monophyletic superphylum called DPANN, for
15 which cultured representatives are not currently available¹². Here, we have targeted viruses
16 infecting *Nanohaloarchaea* cells once our protocol was proven feasible with the
17 appropriate controls (See Supplementary Information and Extended Data Fig. 1).

18 Samples were taken from crystallizer pond CR30 of Bras del Port solar salterns (Santa
19 Pola, Spain), which has been extensively studied by a vast array of microbial ecology
20 techniques¹⁸. A 50 µl sample was used for single cell sorting, generating a total of 936
21 SAGs that were screened for the 16S rRNA gene for identification. A total of 52 SAGs
22 corresponded to *Nanohaloarchaea* (Extended Data Fig. 2) and were used for further
23 analysis. In parallel, individual haloviral genomes present in 2 liters of the same sample

1 were purified, cloned in fosmids and used for the construction of the ‘virochip’. This
2 microarray, containing a total of 384 viral genomes, was hybridized with the pooled
3 genomes of the 52 nanohaloarchaeal SAGs. As shown in Figure 1, one of the fosmids
4 (fosmid C23) yielded a strong hybridization signal. To ascertain which of the
5 *Nanohaloarchaea* was infected with the cloned virus, a new microarray (‘Nanohaloarchaeal
6 chip’) was constructed with the 52 individual genomes (Fig. 1) and hybridized against the
7 purified fosmid C23. Finally, this tentative virus-containing SAG AB578-D14 (henceforth
8 named as D14) and the fosmid insert were sequenced (Supplementary Table 1). As
9 expected, the SAG contained the fosmid insert sequence (i.e. the cloned viral genome) (Fig.
10 2a), indicating that indeed the nanohaloarchaeon D14 was infected at the time of sampling
11 with the cloned virus (we will refer to this virus as ‘nanohaloarchaeal virus 1’, NHV-1).
12 This was further supported by sequencing data that showed that 99.8% of the recovered
13 viral genome from the host D14 was identical to the viral genome cloned in the fosmid and
14 immobilized in the ‘virochip’ (Fig. 2a). Furthermore, data indicated that NHV-1 formed
15 concatamers when infecting its host D14 (Extended Data Fig. 3). In spite of that high level
16 of similarity between both viral genomes (one intracellular, contained within the host D14,
17 and one extracellular, immobilized in the ‘virochip’), a 45 bp region located at the open
18 reading frame (ORF) 8 (Extended Table 1) displayed 11 single nucleotide polymorphisms
19 (SNPs) resulting in three non-synonymous substitutions (Fig. 2 and Extended Data Fig. 4).
20 These two genomes could thus correspond to two different quasi-species of the virus¹⁹ that
21 would be co-occurring in the viral assemblage at the time of sampling. In the case of
22 viruses, a single SNP can impact severely on the viral fitness increasing for instance the
23 adhesion to the host and infection^{20,21}. Genome annotation (Extended Table 1) showed that
24 most of the viral ORFs coded for hypothetical conserved proteins related to other

1 uncultured haloviruses characterized in previous studies⁵⁻⁷. The lack of integrases suggests
2 that NHV-1 is a lytic phage. In addition, the virus possessed a DNA primase and a viral
3 terminase as well as a putative arsenical resistance repressor-like (ORF 7; named as *asrR*).
4 Interestingly, the catalytic domain of this *asrR*-like was highly recruited in different
5 geographically distant viral metagenomes (Fig. 2b) and also in a previously described
6 cellular metagenome of the same crystallizer CR30¹⁸ (identities 77-100%; Fig. 2b).
7 Furthermore, similar *asrR*-like sequences were also found (Supplementary Table S2) in
8 several prokaryote genome contigs from the hypersaline Lake Tyrrell²², where
9 *Nanohaloharchaea* were predominant¹⁷. Arsenic compounds in hypersaline waters are
10 highly prevalent and toxic for organisms, although prokaryotes have evolved different
11 strategies to detoxify or exploit them²³. The fact that the viral *asrR*-like gene resembled that
12 detected in prokaryote genomes and metagenomes suggests a trans-acting regulator with a
13 conserved role in viral fitness that requires further attention. It is also worth noting that the
14 highest recruited NHV-1 genomic region (intergenic space of ORFs 9 and 10) with the
15 cellular metagenome from crystallizer CR30 (Fig. 2) was similar to sequences of the
16 plasmid PL47 of *Hqr. walsbyi* of viral origin²⁴ and a genomic region between the CRISPR
17 3 and the insertion element protein (IS2) of that very abundant square archaeon. In contrast,
18 that viral region was poorly recruited in Lake Tyrrell metaviromes (Fig. 2b), which
19 altogether suggest that this short NHV-1 genomic region could be potentially modulated by
20 the CRISPR-CAS system²⁵ and under strong prey selective pressure of local archaeal
21 assemblages.

22 Small cell and genome sizes have been predicted as unifying features of the DPANN
23 phyla¹². The assembly of the host genome SAG D14 (\approx 1 Mbp; Supplementary Table 3) was

1 similar to that reported for its closest relative *Candidatus* Nanosalinarum spp. J07AB56¹⁷
2 and in the range of *Nanohaloarchaeota* group¹². Genome comparison showed that despite
3 both *Nanohaloarchaea* shared a high 16S rRNA gene sequence identity (Extended Data
4 Fig. 2), significant differences were observed in genetic content (Fig. S6), although in both
5 genomes most genes coded for hypothetical proteins (HP), many of which were shared by
6 both nanohaloarchaea and present in the corresponding CR30 cellular metagenome¹⁸
7 (Extended Data Fig. 7-9 and Supplementary Table 4).

8 As discussed above, GC content and oligonucleotide frequency signatures have been used
9 to tentatively assign virus to hosts in natural assemblages without previous cultivation^{5,7}. In
10 our case, NHV-1 and its nanohaloarchaeon D14 host possessed similar GC content (49 and
11 51% respectively). Principal component analysis of dinucleotide frequencies (Fig. 3)
12 revealed that NHV-1 genome grouped with the genomes of the nanohaloarchaeon D14 host
13 and *Candidatus* Nanosalina (Fig. 3), and also with viral contigs from the above mentioned
14 CR30 viral metagenomic library⁷, which resulted as best BLAST hits for several ORFs of
15 virus NVH-1 (Extended Table 1). Remarkably, the environmental haloviruses eHP-4 and
16 eHP-25, previously assigned to *Nanohaloarchaea* hosts according to their codon usage⁵,
17 also clustered with NHV-1. Thus, our data validate the previous assignments of
18 (uncultured) virus to hosts in hypersaline systems based on genomic signature analyses.

19 One possible limitation of the technique presented here that could mislead the assignment
20 of the virus-host pair is the co-sorting of a cell with a free virus. However, the single-cell
21 sorting mode used here will sort a drop when it contains only one cell in its centre and no
22 other detectable free particles in the drop²⁶, which makes the co-sorting of a cell with a
23 virus very unlikely. Other potential limitations of the technique are the co-sorting of the

1 host cell with unspecific viruses attached to it or with free viruses placed in its shade,
2 known in flow cytometry as ‘swarm’ detection²⁷. However, our microarray hybridization
3 data does not indicate contamination with free viruses, suggesting an insignificant
4 contribution of ‘swarm’ detection during cell sorting. Nevertheless, a simple pre-
5 enrichment step to remove most free viruses could be routinely implemented before sorting,
6 if needed. In the case of unspecific attached viruses, our data does not support that
7 hypothesis but rather confirm previous assignment data⁵. Finally, although our approach
8 has been used to target dsDNA viral assemblages, modifications can be introduced to make
9 it suitable for ssDNA or even RNA viruses²⁸.

10 Here, we have provided a tool that can be used to analyse VMINs over any range of
11 spatiotemporal scales and to draw valuable information on the evolution of virus genomes
12 and the co-evolution with their hosts. This approach can be used to assign viruses to hosts
13 even without previous information on either of them, which makes it suitable for the
14 exploration of the microbial dark matter.

15 **METHODS SUMMARY**

16 Individual cells were separated by means of fluorescence activated cell sorting, lysed and
17 their genomes amplified by multiple displacement amplification⁹⁻¹³. In parallel, viral
18 fraction of the sample was concentrated and individual viral genomes were purified and
19 cloned in fosmids, which were immobilized on a microarray (‘virochip’). Then, a set of
20 microarray hybridizations were performed as depicted in Fig. 1 in order to detect infected
21 cells and assign virus to host in natural uncultured assemblages. Finally, both the cloned
22 virus and the positive-infected individual cell were subjected to Illumina sequencing and
23 downstream analyzed. See Supplementary Information for detailed Methods.

1 **Online Content**

2 Any additional Methods, Extended Data display items and Source Data are available in the
3 online version of the paper; references unique to these sections appear only in the online
4 paper.

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14 **Supplementary Information** is available in the online version of the paper.

15

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23 **Author contribution**

24 MM-G, FS, and JA designed and performed the experiments, analyzed data and wrote the
25 paper. MM-P performed experiments and VP wrote the paper.

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2 **Author information**

3 Reprints and permissions information is available at www.nature.com/reprints. The authors
4 declare no competing financial interests. Readers are welcome to comment on the on line
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7 **Figure Legends**

8 **Figure 1. Experimental design used to assign viruses to hosts in natural assemblages.**

9 Water samples from a crystallizer pond were used for cell sorting and virus concentration.
10 Viral DNA was purified and cloned in fosmids, which were immobilized in the ‘virochip’.
11 Single amplified genomes (SAGs) identified as *Nanohaloarchaea* were pooled and
12 hybridized against the ‘virochip’ yielding a high signal with fosmid C23 (1). Fosmid C23
13 was purified and hybridized against a new chip containing the 52 nanohaloarchaeal SAGs
14 (the ‘Nanohaloarchaeal chip’) (2). A strong hybridization signal was observed in the
15 position of SAG AB578-D14. Both the fosmid C23 and the SAG AB578-D14 were further
16 sequenced and analyzed (3, 4).

17 **Figure 2. Virus NHV-1 infecting nanohaloarchaeon host D14. a,** Mapping of reads from

18 the sequenced host D14 onto the cloned viral genome. A $\geq 99\%$ of identity threshold and
19 ≥ 50 bp read length was used. The near complete viral genome was recovered and
20 reconstructed from the infected cell D14. The gap at ORF 8 (nucleotide positions 7300-
21 7344) indicates a region of high variability (named as GI) since matched reads displayed an
22 average identity of 77% and a total of 11 SNPs were detected (Extended Data Fig. 4). Three

1 more SNPs at positions 7401, 8772 and 9288 are indicated with white arrows. Gaps at
2 ORFs 2 and 3 (178 bp) are likely due to a bias of the MDA reaction since no reads were
3 found to match with the cloned viral genome. Hypothetical and unknown ORF are
4 indicated as 'HP' and 'UN', respectively. **b**, Metagenomic fragment recruitment of NHV-1
5 genome to cellular and viral metagenomes. Data of prokaryote and viral metagenomes from
6 crystallizer CR30 are from Ghai *et al.*¹⁸ and Santos *et al.*⁷, respectively. Percentage of
7 recruited reads (parameters as follows: -e-value 0.001, -perc_identity 60) in the
8 metagenome is depicted in the inner panel. Deep Illumina metavirome sequencing data
9 from Lake Tyrrell (Australia) was from Narasingarao *et al.*¹⁷ under Bioproject accession
10 number PRJNA81851.

11 **Figure 3. Principal component analyses of the dinucleotide frequency signatures of**
12 **viruses and hosts.** Frequency dinucleotide signatures were calculated and plotted in a PCA
13 plot for reference halophilic prokaryote genomes, the pair NHV-1-Nanohaloarchaon host
14 D14 and the viral contigs from environmental uncultured halophages (“eHP-*number*” and
15 “Contig_*number*”) from García-Heredia *et al.*⁵ and Santos *et al.*,²⁹ respectively. Viral and
16 host genomes are represented by spheres and hosts, respectively.

17 **Extended Data Figures**

18 **Extended Data Figure 1. Design of the ‘control microarray’.** **a**, Genomic DNA from the
19 strain M8 of *S. ruber* and a fosmid containing the *S. ruber* M8 virus Φ M8CR4 were used as
20 probes and spotted in the array from 5 different concentration solutions (each group of 5
21 grey and black circles inside the boxes have the same DNA amount). **b**, Hybridization
22 between the ‘control microarray’ and genomic DNA from a non-infected *S. ruber* M8, used

1 as the ‘target’. **c**, Hybridization between the ‘control microarray’ and total DNA from a *S.*
2 *ruber* M8 culture infected with virus ΦM8CR4, used as the ‘target’.

3 **Extended Data Figure 2. Phylogenetic analyses of 16S rRNA gene from SAGs**
4 **belonging to *Nanohaloarchaea* group.** The neighbor-joining consensus tree was built with
5 a bootstrap value of 1000. Bootstrap values ≥ 50 are displayed. The positive-detected
6 infected cell is indicated (red arrow). 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity with
7 *Nanosalinarum* J07AB56 was 98%.

8 **Extended Data Figure 3. Concatamers of virus NHV-1 infecting host cell D14.** Upper
9 diagram represents the genome of virus NHV-1 cloned in fosmid C23. Nucleotide position
10 numbers are referred to the sequenced genome of the cloned virus C23. Illumina reads
11 overlapping (100% identity) the beginning and the end of the virus NHV-1 infecting host
12 D14 (depicted below) indicate that a viral concatamer was formed in the cell.

13 **Extended Data Figure 4. Genomic island signature in ORF 8 of the virus infecting the**
14 **nanohalarchaeon SAG D14. a**, A total of 2685 reads recovered from the infected cell D14
15 were found to match to the nucleotide position region 7300-7344 of the cloned virus with
16 an average nucleotide identity of 77% with a total of 11 SNPs, indicating a region of high
17 variability of the virus and a probable signature to differentiate variants of the virus. **b**,
18 Protein alignment of ORF 8 for two viral variant indicating the three non-synonymous
19 substitutions at positions 71, 77 and 80.

1 **Extended Data Figure 5. Sequencing coverage of the genome SAG D14.** An artificial
2 concatenated of contigs were performed. Identity threshold of 95% and minimum read
3 overlap of 50 bp were applied.

4 **Extended Data Figure 6. Genomic comparison of nanohaloarchaeon host D14 with the**
5 **closest relative nanohaloarchaeon *Candidatus Nanosalinarum* spp. a,** Average
6 nucleotide identity (ANI) values were performed with JSpecies package as described in
7 details in Supplementary Information. ANI between both nanohaloarchaea was 80.5%.
8 Large contigs of nanohaloarchaeon SAG AB578-D14 genome were artificially sectioned in
9 1,020 nucleotide fragments resulting in a total of 1552 fragments that were compared by
10 BLAST against the reference genome of *Candidatus Nanosalinarum* spp. (J07AB56). **b,**
11 Tetranucleotide frequency signature correlation for the pairwise genome comparison. The
12 average tetranucleotide frequency between the two *Nanohaloarchaea* was 0.86.

13 **Extended Data Figure 7. Genome annotation of nanohaloarchaeon host D14.**
14 Annotation was performed in SEED subsystem (RAST) and Integrated Microbial Genomes
15 (IMG) of JGI. CDs previously annotated as hypothetical proteins were assigned to
16 conserved proteins (a total of 198) when identity threshold and coverage values were $\geq 70\%$
17 with *Candidatus Nanosalinarum* J07AB56.

18 **Extended Data Figure 8. Distribution of CDs annotated as hypothetical proteins in**
19 **SEED subsystem according to contig size for SAG D14 genome assembly.** Hypothetical
20 proteins were overrepresented in contig >1000 bp, which might indicate that hypothetical
21 proteins in SAG D14 might be overestimated as a result of genome fragmentation likely
22 due to MDA bias and viral infection.

1 **Extended Data Figure 9. Metagenome analysis of annotated hypothetical proteins**
 2 **(HP) of host D14.** Annotated HP of host D14 were searched and compared with the
 3 cellular metagenome from the same site (crystallizer CR30). Over 60% of total annotated
 4 CDs as HP genes in host D14 were found in the corresponding CR30 cellular metagenome
 5 displaying high sequence identities.

6

7 **Extended Data Tables**

Extended Table 1: Genome annotation of NHV-1 infecting nanohaloarchaeon AB 578-D14

ORF	Nucleotide position	Annotation ¹	Best hit (coverage/identity) ²
1	52-342	Hypothetical archaeal protein	82/37 <i>Haloarcula vallismortis</i>
2	561-4595	DNA primase*	88/53 Halophilic archaeon DL31
3	4939-5313	Hypothetical viral protein	98/82 Uncultured halovirus (contig 157)
4	5310-5675	NAD dependent epimerase	44/33 <i>Liefsonia xyli</i>
5	5672-5818	Unknown	Unknown
6	6319-6546	Hypothetical viral protein	100/96 Uncultured halovirus (contig 152)
		Hypothetical viral protein	86/42 Uncultured halovirus (contig 152)
7	6539-6922	Arsenical resistance protein repressor*	51/50 <i>Halococcus saccharolyticus</i>
8	7099-7650	Hypothetical viral protein	93/51 Environmental halophage EHP-16, 6 ,12
9	7881-8174	Hypothetical viral protein	100/79 Uncultured halovirus (contig 42)
10	8550-10019	Viral terminase*	99/92 Uncultured halovirus (contig 11)

¹Presence of the catalytic domain detection is indicated with an asterisk (CDS-BLAST and SWISS-PROT BLAST)

²BLAST data from Uniprot and Genbank databases

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